

THE CONCEPT OF "WOMEN'S SOCIAL MOBILITY"

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Abstract. *This article provides information about the sources of social mobility, the motivation to achieve, the law of increasing needs, and the hierarchical system of distribution of social results. The presence of channels of social mobility in society, including various social institutions - the military, religion, education, political organizations, trade unions, family, marriage, art, sports, inheritance, elections, mass media, social networks, social networks of individuals and their groups. creates conditions for movement.*

Keywords: *Social mobility, mobility channels, social institution, hierarchical system, social process.*

КОНЦЕПЦИЯ «ЖЕНСКОЙ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ МОБИЛЬНОСТИ»

Аннотация. *В статье представлены сведения об источниках социальной мобильности, мотивации достижения, законе возрастания потребностей и иерархической системе распределения социальных результатов. Наличие каналов социальной мобильности в обществе, включая различные социальные институты - армия, религия, образование, политические организации, профсоюзы, семья, брак, искусство, спорт, наследование, выборы, средства массовой информации, социальные сети, социальные сети отдельных лиц. и их группы. создает условия для движения.*

Ключевые слова: *Социальная мобильность, каналы мобильности, социальный институт, иерархическая система, социальный процесс.*

Financial actions that change the status of a young person constitute the essence of economic mobility. In modern conditions, this is also confirmed by the results of various social studies, the economic status of an individual is determined by the most important indicators such as his income, the form of ownership of the enterprise he works for, and his attitude to property.

The following factors serve as factors of women's growing social mobility: political and economic stability, a wide range of mobility in society, a high level of parental education, material well-being, living in an urban area, being employed in the field of commerce or private entrepreneurship, having certain personal qualities (diligence, aspiration, communication, flexibility, readiness for changes). Factors of decreasing mobility are sudden changes in the social structure of society, political and economic recessions, the lack of training of specialists in certain professions to the needs of the labor market, lack of higher education in parents, below average level of material security, living in rural areas, employment in the budget sector, low starting salary of young employees, laziness, lack of initiative, lack of ambition, etc.

Political mobility refers to changes in individuals or social groups. The political position is explained by the powers of authority that this or that person has. Currently, not only officials in the state administration system, but also leaders of political parties, managers of military and law enforcement agencies, large corporations, media leaders, etc. have high political positions.

Increasing powers of authority is an integral aspect of moving up the service ladder, one of the indicators of professional mobility. Therefore, models of political stratification and political mobility are explained with great uncertainty.

Actions affecting the change of professional positions of individuals or social groups are manifested in professional mobility. One of the types of professional mobility of women is job change. This mobility may be associated with a change in job or specialty, or with the persistence of these symptoms. One of the important indicators of professional mobility is the service career - the transition from an executive job to a managerial job. Professional mobility is explained by an increase in the individual's qualifications, the improvement of professional skills, thereby gaining a higher rank, title, academic degree, etc.

One of the most important aspects characteristic of an individual in modern societies is the level of education, and its change is educational mobility. The educational status of a person in Uzbekistan is explained by the existence of basic, general secondary, secondary special vocational, higher education and post-university education levels. An additional factor affecting education and professional mobility is training and retraining courses. As one of the directions of women's educational mobility, moving from one educational institution to another based on the prestige of the educational place, such actions can increase or decrease the educational status of a person.

The change in the social status of women in various spheres of society's life compared to the status of their parents constitutes intergenerational mobility. Intergenerational mobility is an important factor of social change and a manifestation of social activity of individuals. The change in the social status of children compared to the social status of their parents is one of the indicators of a rapidly developing society.

Based on the number of participants, social mobility is divided into individual mobility (actions of individuals) and collective mobility (changes in the status of social groups, classes).

Various factors influence the mobility of individuals and groups.

First, there is a system of stratification, which is manifested in the importance attached to a predetermined and achieved position. When societal institutions focus heavily on established status, collective or group mobility tendencies emerge. Individual mobility tends to prevail in societies with a strong emphasis on achieved status.

Second, social background (race, nationality, age, etc.) appears as an obstacle to individual mobility. Therefore, some social strata strive for collective mobility so that the predetermined status of group members does not hinder their success. Examples of this are various movements, including those fighting to restore and preserve the rights of national and racial minorities, fighting for more rights for women, etc. The success of these actions indicates that collective efforts can change the status quo.

Third, different social groups are unstable to changes in the status of social groups (revolution, war, military rebellion, coup d'état, rallies, demonstrations, etc.) have an impact.

Depending on the level of influence of the state on social movements, social mobility will be chaotic and organized. Organized mobility is carried out in two ways:

- a) with the consent of the people;
- b) without their consent.

In a narrow sense, the concept of "women's social mobility" is used in two senses. First, it is a social movement that changes the social position of the subject, first of all a young person.

Secondly, this concept refers to one of the stages of the process of women's social dynamics, that is, the ability to act.

Therefore, it depends on women to act on their own and the state and society to create sufficient conditions for women's social movement. It also depends on the capital invested by the parents in their children for social activities and the ability of the children to assimilate this invested capital.

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